

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 136

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 136

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 136:1 "Give thanks to the LORD, for ^bHe is good, For His lovingkindness is everlasting. ² Give thanks to the "God of gods, For His lovingkindness is everlasting. ³ Give thanks to the "Lord of lords, For His lovingkindness is everlasting. ⁴ To Him who "alone does great ¹wonders, For His lovingkindness is everlasting; ⁵ To Him who "made the heavens ^{1b}with skill, For His lovingkindness is everlasting; ⁶ To Him who "spread out the earth above the waters, For His lovingkindness is everlasting; ⁷ To Him who "made <i>the</i> great lights, For His lovingkindness is everlasting; ⁸ The "sun to rule ¹by day, For His lovingkindness is everlasting, ⁹ The "moon and stars to rule ¹by night, For His lovingkindness is everlasting.</p>	<p>Psa. 136:1 הוֹדוּ לַיהוָה כִּי־טוֹב כִּי לְעוֹלָם תְּסֻדּוּ : ² הוֹדוּ לֵאלֹהֵי הָאֱלֹהִים כִּי לְעוֹלָם תְּסֻדּוּ : ³ הוֹדוּ לְאֱדֹנָי הָאֱדֹנִים כִּי לְעוֹלָם תְּסֻדּוּ : ⁴ לַעֲשֵׂה נִפְלְאוֹת גְּדֹלוֹת לְבָדּוּ כִּי לְעוֹלָם תְּסֻדּוּ : ⁵ לַעֲשֵׂה הַשָּׁמַיִם בְּתַבּוּנָה כִּי לְעוֹלָם תְּסֻדּוּ : ⁶ לְרַקַּע הָאָרֶץ עַל־הַמַּיִם כִּי לְעוֹלָם תְּסֻדּוּ : ⁷ לַעֲשֵׂה אוֹרִים גְּדֹלִים כִּי לְעוֹלָם תְּסֻדּוּ : ⁸ אֶת־הַשָּׁמַשׁ לְמַמְשֶׁלֶת בַּיּוֹם כִּי לְעוֹלָם תְּסֻדּוּ : ⁹ אֶת־הַיָּרֵחַ וְכּוֹכָבִים לְמַמְשֶׁלֶת בַּלַּיְלָה כִּי לְעוֹלָם תְּסֻדּוּ : ¹⁰ לְמַכּוֹה מִצָּרִים בְּבִכּוּרֵיהֶם כִּי לְעוֹלָם תְּסֻדּוּ : ¹¹ וַיּוֹצֵא יִשְׂרָאֵל מִמִּצְרַיִם כִּי לְעוֹלָם תְּסֻדּוּ : ¹² בְּיַד תְּזַקֶּה וּבְזֵרוּעַ נְטוּיָהּ כִּי לְעוֹלָם תְּסֻדּוּ : ¹³ לְגִזְרַיִם־סוּף לְגִזְרֵיהֶם כִּי לְעוֹלָם תְּסֻדּוּ : ¹⁴ וְהָעֶבֶר יִשְׂרָאֵל בְּתוֹכוֹ כִּי לְעוֹלָם תְּסֻדּוּ : ¹⁵ וְנֹעַר פָּרְעֹה וַחֲתִילוֹ בַּיַּם־סוּף כִּי לְעוֹלָם תְּסֻדּוּ : ¹⁶ לְמוֹלִיד עַמּוֹ בַּמִּדְבָּר כִּי לְעוֹלָם תְּסֻדּוּ : ¹⁷ לְמַכּוֹת מְלָכִים גְּדֹלִים כִּי לְעוֹלָם תְּסֻדּוּ : ¹⁸ וַיַּהַרְג מְלָכִים</p>
<p>Psa. 136:10 To Him who "smote ¹the Egyptians in their firstborn,</p>	

<p>For His lovingkindness is everlasting, ¹¹ And ^abrought Israel out from their midst, For His lovingkindness is everlasting, ¹² With a ^astrong hand and an ^boutstretched arm, For His lovingkindness is everlasting. ¹³ To Him who ^adivided the ¹Red Sea ²asunder, For His lovingkindness is everlasting, ¹⁴ And ^amade Israel pass through the midst of it, For His lovingkindness is everlasting; ¹⁵ But ^aHe ¹overthrew Pharaoh and his army in the ²Red Sea, For His lovingkindness is everlasting. ¹⁶ To Him who ^aled His people through the wilderness, For His lovingkindness is everlasting; ¹⁷ To Him who ^asmote great kings, For His lovingkindness is everlasting, ¹⁸ And ^aslew ¹mighty kings, For His lovingkindness is everlasting: ¹⁹ ^aSihon, king of the Amorites, For His lovingkindness is everlasting, ²⁰ And ^aOg, king of Bashan, For His lovingkindness is everlasting, ²¹ And ^agave their land as a heritage, For His lovingkindness is everlasting,</p>	<p>אֲדִירִים כִּי לְעוֹלָם חֶסֶדּוֹ : ¹⁹ לְסִיחּוֹן מִלְּךְ הָאֲמֹרִי כִי לְעוֹלָם חֶסֶדּוֹ : ²⁰ וְלַעֲוֹג מִלְּךְ חֶבְשָׁן כִּי לְעוֹלָם חֶסֶדּוֹ : ²¹ וְנָתַן אֶרְצָם לְנַחֲלָה כִּי לְעוֹלָם חֶסֶדּוֹ : ²² גַּחְלָה לְיִשְׂרָאֵל עֲבָדוֹ כִּי לְעוֹלָם חֶסֶדּוֹ : ²³ שִׁבְשִׁבְלָנוּ זָכַר לָנוּ כִּי לְעוֹלָם חֶסֶדּוֹ : ²⁴ וַיִּפְרֹקֵנוּ מִצָּרֵינוּ כִּי לְעוֹלָם חֶסֶדּוֹ : ²⁵ נָתַן לָחֶם לְכָל־ בָּשָׂר כִּי לְעוֹלָם חֶסֶדּוֹ : ²⁶ הוֹדֵרוּ לְאֵל הַשָּׁמַיִם כִּי לְעוֹלָם חֶסֶדּוֹ :</p>
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<p>²² Even a heritage to Israel His ^aservant, For His lovingkindness is everlasting.</p> <p>Psa. 136:23 Who ^aremembered us in our low estate, For His lovingkindness is everlasting,</p> <p>²⁴ And has ^arescued us from our adversaries, For His lovingkindness is everlasting;</p> <p>²⁵ Who ^agives food to all flesh, For His lovingkindness is everlasting.</p> <p>²⁶ Give thanks to the ^aGod of heaven, For His lovingkindness is everlasting.</p>	
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References

Psalm 136:1

^a1 Chr 16:34; Ps 106:1; 107:1; 118:1; Jer 33:11

^b2 Chr 5:13; 7:3; Ezra 3:11; Ps 100:5

^c1 Chr 16:41; 2 Chr 20:21; Ps 118:1-4

Psalm 136:2

^aDeut 10:17

Psalm 136:3

^aDeut 10:17

Psalm 136:4

¹I.e. wonderful acts

^aDeut 6:22; Job 9:10; Ps 72:18

Psalm 136:5

¹Lit *with understanding*

^aGen 1:1

^bPs 104:24; Prov 3:19; Jer 10:12; 51:15

Psalm 136:6

^aGen 1:2, 6, 9; Ps 24:2; Is 42:5; 44:24; Jer 10:12

Psalm 136:7

^aGen 1:14-18; Ps 74:16

Psalm 136:8

¹Or *over the*

^aGen 1:16

Psalm 136:9

¹Or *over the*

^aGen 1:16

Psalm 136:10

¹Lit *Egypt*

^aEx 12:29; Ps 78:51; 135:8

Psalm 136:11

^aEx 12:51; 13:3; Ps 105:43

Psalm 136:12

^aEx 6:1; 13:9; 1 Kin 8:42; Neh 1:10; Ps 44:3; Jer 32:21

^bEx 6:6; Deut 4:34; 5:15; 7:19; 9:29; 11:2; 2 Kin 17:36; 2 Chr 6:32; Jer 32:17

Psalm 136:13

¹Lit *Sea of Reeds*

²Lit *in parts*

^aEx 14:21; Ps 66:6; 78:13

Psalm 136:14

^aEx 14:22; Ps 106:9

Psalm 136:15

¹Lit *shook off*

²Lit *Sea of Reeds*

^aEx 14:27; Ps 78:53; 106:11

Psalm 136:16

^aEx 13:18; 15:22; Deut 8:15; Ps 78:52

Psalm 136:17

^aPs 135:10-12; 136:17-22

Psalm 136:18

¹Lit *majestic*

^aDeut 29:7

Psalm 136:19

^aNum 21:21-24

Psalm 136:20

^aNum 21:33-35

Psalm 136:21

^aJosh 12:1

Psalm 136:22

^aPs 105:6; Is 41:8; 44:1; 45:4

Psalm 136:23

“Ps 9:12; 103:14; 106:45

Psalm 136:24

“Judg 6:9; Neh 9:28; Ps 107:2

Psalm 136:25

“Ps 104:27; 145:15

Psalm 136:26

“Gen 24:3, 7; 2 Chr 36:23; Ezra 1:2; 5:11; Neh 1:4

Targum

Psa. 136:1 Sing praise in the presence of the LORD, for he is good, for his goodness is forever. ² Sing praise to the God of gods, for his goodness is forever. ³ Sing praise to the Lord of lords, for his goodness is forever. ⁴ To him who did great wonders by himself, for his goodness is forever. ⁵ To him who made the heavens by insight, for his goodness is forever. ⁶ To him who made firm the earth on the waters, for his goodness is forever. ⁷ To him who made great lights, for his goodness is forever. ⁸ The sun to rule by day, for his goodness is forever. ⁹ The moon and stars to rule by night, for his goodness is forever. ¹⁰ To him who smites the Egyptians with plagues, killing the firstborn, for his goodness is forever. ¹¹ And brought out Israel redeemed from among them, for his goodness is forever. ¹² With a mighty hand and upraised arm, for his goodness is forever. ¹³ To him who split the Sea of Reeds into pieces, for his goodness is forever. ¹⁴ And made Israel cross over in the middle of it, for his goodness is forever. ¹⁵ And choked Pharaoh and his forces in the Sea of Reeds, for his goodness is forever. ¹⁶ To him who led his people in the wilderness, for his goodness is forever. ¹⁷ To him who smites great kings, for his goodness is forever. ¹⁸ And slew proud kings, for his goodness is forever. ¹⁹ Namely, Sihon the Amorite king, for his goodness is forever. ²⁰ And Og, king of Mathnan, for his goodness is forever. ²¹ And gave their land as an inheritance, for his goodness is forever. ²² An inheritance to Israel his servant, for his goodness is forever. ²³ In our humiliation he remembered his covenant with us, for his goodness is forever. ²⁴ And redeemed us from our oppressors, for his goodness is forever. ²⁵ Who gives his food to all flesh, for his goodness is forever. ²⁶ Sing praise to the God of heaven, for his goodness is forever.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm is twenty-six verses. This corresponds to the numerical value of the Four-letter name of the LORD. This designates that the LORD is the creator of Heaven and Earth. The Psalm is a collection of events from creation to Israel's conquest of Canaan.

Notes on this Psalm

Verse one – the Psalmist starts by acknowledging the LORD's love through the Sefirah Chesed. The Psalmist does this for all the verses of the Psalm.

Acknowledge it to God that He is good, that His loving-kindness from the Sefirah Chesed endures forever.

The message is that the loving-kindness of the LORD comes from the Sefirah Chesed and it will last forever.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

